

Week 1 – Introduction to QGIS – digitising and creating data

Written by: Adam Peacock

Contact email: A.J.Peacock@keele.ac.uk

Week 1 Instructions:

Welcome to the citizen science training program! As discussed in the accompanying lecture, this training is going to provide you with an introduction to the complex, yet exceptionally interesting world of G.I.S. You will be engaging with G.I.S through the medium of a piece of software titled **QGIS** – or Quantum Geographic Information System - a particularly friendly (and free!) interface for any first-time user. As with anything new, try not to be too intimidated at first – once you understand how the menu works, what the key terms mean and the logic behind running QGIS, it becomes an enjoyable experience. These workshops have been designed for **absolute beginners**, meaning that it will remain brief and fairly straight forward. It will hopefully give you the foundations to move further in G.I.S should you wish to. Remember - we are here to help!

Before we start, a few important housekeeping rules. These will save you a lot of anguish later down the road! Firstly, any GIS software you use has the potential to crash – particularly if you try to do too much at once. That “shouldn’t” be a problem here, but like any software, sometimes there is no explanation for why the software crashes... Even we may not know! Nonetheless, there are a couple of work arounds for this. Please carefully read the following before beginning exercise 1 (we have covered these in the lecture also!):

1) **Try to use a memory stick or hard drive for each session.** Not only will this avoid clutter on your computer (we may be working with some big file sizes!) but QGIS just runs better this way. This practical should be fine without one, but please be aware if the practical does not run in the future, my advice will generally be to ensure you are using a memory stick.

2) **File organisation.** This is absolutely essential. QGIS works by reading where files are located on your computer/ hard drive – what we call their ‘directory’. For example, storing something in ‘my documents’ or ‘pictures’ on your computer. To this end, it is very important that you organise your files using the rules below:

- Think carefully about folder layout. Make a specific folder titled “GIS” on your computer or external storage. I then recommend a series of folders within this folder titled “week 1”, “week 2”, etc. This will make things much easier to find! **Do this now before proceeding!**
- Think carefully about the file names you use. A file you create of ‘roads’ around the Rugeley titled “GIS 134678” might be quick and convenient at the time, but when you come back to editing a piece of work weeks later, it will be difficult to remember what the file actually is. Instead, “Roads_Rugeley” might be more applicable. Be specific and you will save yourself hours of frustration! More importantly, once you have named a file, try not to rename it or move where it is stored. This can really irritate the software and corrupt data!
- Extracting folders. In order to move bulk data sets faster, files are often “zipped” and “compressed”. This will be indicated by the folder having a zip icon like this . You need to ensure you unzip these folders. You can do so by right clicking on the folder < clicking extract all < then choosing where to save the file. QGIS may not be able to read the data if you do not do this!

3) **Save often!** Please get in to the habit of regularly saving your work. This is good practice, but especially with QGIS. **Save, save, save** – in the event of the software crashing, you can simply close it and load your project again. Simply go to project < save as < and name your file (week 1, week 2 etc.)

Overall, **forward planning is essential to the success of being a citizen scientist.** Be organised!

Practical one: digitizing a map of Rugeley.

As explained in lecture 1, a digitization is a method of creating what we refer to as a “shapefile”, a vector format of data. **This will explained in more depth in coming weeks – do not panic!** For now, you simply need to know that this week we will be creating a series of different ‘vector files’ to indicate different features of part of Rugeley– simple! Think of it as being an advanced version of Microsoft Paint, but we create each layer one at a time.

Today we're going to be tracing over a map of Rugeley and creating data. This might seem overly simple, but it is something that is critical to master in QGIS!

Part one: Adding data to QGIS.

The great thing about QGIS is that it can handle lots of different pieces of information – or data – at any one time. This is useful because it allows us to compare things that would otherwise be difficult to compare. In order to complete this practical, you'll need to have something to trace over! So, we'll be using none other than Google Maps!

1. Load up QGIS. Click project < new. Your screen should look like this!

Figure 1: What the QGIS interface looks like.

I'll admit, it isn't that exciting... but this is a really powerful tool... promise! The big empty white box in the middle of your screen is known as the **Map area**.

Project Edit View Layer Settings Plugins Vector Raster Database Web Mesh Processing Help

This is the **menu toolbar** – this is where we can change settings, perform analyses, etc.

Underneath it is the **project toolbar**, this is where specific tools are stored, usually to move around the map, save our work, zoom in and out, etc.

Remember these! I would recommend taking time to have a look at both!

2. **Now is the time to save your project. Remember – save, save, save! Go to: Project < save as < week 1. Save it in the correct folder (the one you made earlier!).**

Figure 2: Where the save button is on QGIS

Figure 3: What the save menu looks like in QGIS. The part in hashed lines on figure 3 is where you can navigate to your GIS folder on your computer/ memory stick.

At this point, we also want to set the **Coordinate Reference System – CRS**. A CRS is how QGIS can tell where we are in the world. It's like putting your home address into Google Maps so it knows where you are! A CRS make sure all our data stays in the right place.

3. Go to project < properties.

Figure 4. Where the properties menu is in QGIS.

4. The menu below in figure 5 should pop up. On the left, select CRS (first hashed box on figure 5).
5. Where it says filter (second hashed box on figure 5), type in EPSG:27700.
6. You should have OSGB 1936 / British National Grid. Click it.

7. Click apply (down the bottom), then click ok (next to apply).

Figure 5: What the CRS menu looks like.

Now that is done, let's add the Google map layer to your project!

To do this, you'll need the 'browser' window. Not to be confused with the evil creature from Super Mario. This looks like figure 6 below.

Figure 6: The browser window.

If you do not see the browser window, you may need to active it. You can find it in:

View <
tick
(Figure 7

Panels <
browser.
below)

Figure 7: Where to find the browser panel.

8. On the browser window, **right** click on XYZ tiles.

Figure 8: Where the XYZ tiles is.

The following steps can be found on figure 9 below if you get stuck!

9. Choose New Connection.

10. In the XYZ connection window, enter Google maps where it says Name.

11. Where it says URL, copy and paste the following:

<https://mt1.google.com/vt/lyrs=r&x={x}&y={y}&z={z}>

What you are doing here is telling QGIS **where** it can find Google Maps **online**. This is really useful because it can tap into online databases as well as those on your computer!

12. Set the Max. Zoom level to 19. This tells QGIS how far out to zoom the map. I have selected this to show you how the world is quite literally at your disposal!

13. Click ok.

Don't panic if nothing has popped up! You should see Google maps under your XYZ Tiles area (figure 9 below)

Figure 9: Google maps under XYZ tiles.

14. Left click on Google maps (as above) and drag it right to the map area.

If all has gone as planned, you should see a map of the world appear!

This is a good opportunity to learn how to move around the map. After all, we'd like to get to Rugeley!

15. You'll need to click the pan. Tool. It looks like a hand.

Figure 10: Where the pan tool is on the tool bar.

16. Move your mouse so it is over the UK. Don't worry if your geography isn't great – we've got your back! (Figure 11 below).

Figure 11: Where the UK is.

17. Using the mouse, start scrolling in, further and further. You should start getting closer to the UK. If you are using a laptop touch pad, move two fingers in opposite directions. If things go too far, you can zoom out by doing the opposite action. If you move off centre from the UK, click and drag the map, which moves you around. **Spend 5 minutes getting used to these features!**

18. When ready, start zooming in towards Rugeley. It's around here (figure 12).

Figure 12: Where Rugeley is (roughly) in the UK.

19. You'll want to zoom/ pan to roughly the spot in figure 13.

Figure 13. Ahhh, wonderful Rugeley!

Part two: digitizing

20. Before we begin digitizing, go to settings > options and go to the digitizing tab as below.

Figure 14: Where 'options' is located under the settings tab.

21. Tick enable snapping by default

22. Set default snap mode to vertex and segment. This tells the software to assist you with creating vector files and to guide you as you do so.

Figure 15: The digitizing options.

We are now ready to begin 'digitizing'. Effectively we will be tracing over certain features to highlight them more effectively on the map. This is a way of creating spatial data. Where we once had a base map, we can now create layers which can allow us to perform new operations. You will learn the value of this in the coming weeks! The River Trent is a good start!

23. Go to Layer > create layer > new shapefile layer. The following window should appear...

Figure 16: Make sure you save!

24. Name the shapefile **river**

25. Set the geometry type to polyline. We are digitizing a river, so a line makes sense!

26. Click the “...” symbol next to where you named the file (See figure 16 for reference) and tell QGIS to save into your GIS folder, else it will come up with an error!

You should see river appear on the left under ‘layers’:

Figure 17: Where the layers panel is.

27. Click this symbol at the top of the screen. This is the toggle editing button. This tells QGIS you would like to edit the selected layer – in this case the river layer we just made.

28. Now click the Add Feature button . This tells QGIS to let you begin digitizing a shapefile.

29. Then, start clicking on the left-hand section of the River Trent and continue to click and trace the River. Every time you click, you create a 'node'.

30. Once you reach the end, right click.

31. When the window pops up, simply click ok. You will notice that there is now a line on the river. Congratulations, you just created a shapefile!

32. The line is quite difficult to distinguish, however. We can edit this by right clicking on the river file on the left (in the layers panel).

33. Click properties < Symbology.

34. Increase the line thickness to 3.66.

35. Set the colour to Blue. We will learn more about cartographic (map) principles later in the training.

36. When you are happy, click ok.

37. Now, click Save Layer Edits and then **save your project**.

You will notice that if you untick the raster map layer in the layers panel (on the left), the river shapefile you made remains there. You have created a layer.

We will now make more layers. Think of it as if you are stacking bits of paper with different symbols on to then form a map.

Part three: Digitize more!

Now you know how to create a shapefile, we can add more features to our map.

Let's try another. It would be useful to mark the buildings. There are a lot here, so do enough to distinguish them and make the buildings prominent on the map. Follow the same steps for creating a shapefile layer as before **BUT WITH ONE CHANGE:**

This time, make sure you set the Geometry type to **polygon** rather than **polyline**. You can trace around buildings using similar method to previously, however, this tells the software to try to create a box rather than a line. You will see the difference when you begin. **Remember to click the "...” icon and select your week 1 folder to tell QGIS where to save the shapefile – else you may get an error.**

Click the edit button (notice how it says polygon rather than polyline (this is because we told QGIS to do so!) Trace around the buildings on the map. When you are done, remember to save layers edits

and then **SAVE YOUR PROJECT. Do as many as you would like to until you are comfortable with the tool.**

Great work, you have now created two shapefiles. I would like you to also digitize the following:

- A56 – polyline
- A460/ Hednesford Road – polyline
- The powerstation site – polygon
- The canal - polyline

Remember to save edits and save your project regularly.

Usually we would finish any work on QGIS by making a map. However, I think this is probably enough for today. Well done!

I hope you enjoyed your introduction to QGIS – you will be a GIS pro before you know it.

Please save your project as we may return to it at a later practical.

Remember, if you forget how to create shapefiles at any point in a later practical, you can always use these instructions again!